

Fig. 1. Photometric titration of Be²⁺
Be²⁺ = 2.0 mg, CAS = 0.500 mg,
pH = 4.0, λ = 570 nm, total volume = 50 ml
Be²⁺ found = 2.0 mg.

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Estimation of p-Benzoquinone with Titanium(III) Chloride

N. KRISHNA MURTY, Y. PULLA RAO and V. SATYANARAYANA

Department of Chemistry, Andhra University, Waltair. 530 003.

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KNECHT and Hibbert¹ estimated quinone with titanium(III) chloride using methylene blue as indicator. They had taken the aqueous solution of benzoquinone to which added a very dilute methylene blue solution and titrated with titanium(III) chloride till methylene blue was decolourised. Incidentally we have found that the results were 1.5-2.0% high because of the slow reaction between the indicator and titanium (III). So in the light of which we have studied the reaction in detail and the methods for the accurate determination of quinone using some more indicators are given.

Experimental

About 0.06N p-benzoquinone solution is prepared and standardised iodometrically², 0.1 N titanium(III) chloride in 2.0 N HCl. standardised with potassium dichromate³, 0.2% aqueous cacotheline solution and 0.1% aqueous solutions of methylene blue, thionine, variamine blue, neutral red, phenosafranine and safranine-T are used.

Procedure : An aliquot volume of quinone is taken in the titration vessel which is fitted with a three holed rubber stopper, one hole accommodates the tip of the microburette, through the other two holes pass the inlet and outlet tubes for carbon dioxide. Then required volume of 1 : 1 HCl. or 1 : 3 H₂SO₄ is added to the titration vessel in the case of all indicators, so that the overall acid concentration is 1.0 N in a total volume of 40 ml. 0.3 ml. of cacotheline or 0.05 ml. of other indicators are added in each case and the required amount of oxalic acid is added so that the overall oxalic acid concentration is 0.01 M in the case of methylene blue, cacotheline and thionine and 0.10 M in the case of variamine blue, neutral red, phenosafranine and safranine-T. Carbon dioxide is passed through the contents for 10 min. The titration is then carried out with titanium(III) chloride solution to the appearance of pink colour in the case of cacotheline and to the disappearance of the dye colour in all other cases. In the case of variamine blue 0.3 ml. of indicator should

TABLE 1—ESTIMATION OF QUINONE WITH TiCl₃ IN N HCl AND 1 N H₂SO₄.

Indicator	1 N HCl medium	
	taken	found
Methylene blue.	4.342	4.349
	39.08	39.10
Cacotheline.	6.513	6.518
	39.10	39.12
Thionine.	4.103	4.111
	36.72	36.67
Variamine blue.	3.129	3.132
	27.63	27.52
Neutral red.	3.068	3.064
	28.22	28.31
Phenosafranine.	3.068	3.060
	27.61	27.70
Safranine-T	4.400	4.412
	27.65	27.74
	1 N H ₂ SO ₄ medium	
Methylene blue.	4.342	4.345
	39.08	39.12
Cacotheline.	6.513	6.518
	39.10	39.14
Thionine.	6.154	6.150
	28.72	28.63
Variamine blue.	3.375	3.380
	28.29	28.39
Neutral red.	3.313	3.323
	27.61	27.50
Phenosafranine.	3.405	3.412
	27.64	27.72
Safranine-T.	5.281	5.291
	39.60	39.50

NOTES

be preferably added near the equivalence point as a part of the indicator is found to be destroyed if added in the beginning. Some typical results are presented in Table 1.

Discussion

According to the method¹, the results obtained for quinone are 1.5-2.0% high. The high values may be due to the following possibilities. 1) The reaction between quinone and titanium(III) chloride may be slow. 2) The reaction between methylene blue and titanium(III) may be slow or 3) The reaction between methylene blue and titanium(III) may be retarded by the presence of hydroquinone. We have studied the reaction between quinone and titanium(III) potentiometrically under different conditions and have found that the reaction between quinone and titanium (III) is fast enough to carry out the estimation to an accurate value.

Preliminary studies made by us revealed that there is no effect of the presence of hydroquinone on the speed of the reaction between methylene blue and titanium(III) chloride. From the separate experiments we have found that the reaction between methylene blue and titanium(III) chloride is slow (which takes about 30 sec. for the disappearance of blue colour of methylene blue, when titanium(III) is added). Rao and Rao⁴ found that the reaction between titanium(III) chloride and the dyes (neutral red, phenosafranine and safranin-T) was catalysed by the presence of 0.1M overall oxalic acid concentration. So, we tried the effect of oxalic acid concentration on the reaction between titanium (III) and methylene blue, and found that the disappearance of methylene blue colour with titanium(III) is instantaneous in the presence of 0.005 M overall oxalic acid concentration. We have studied the effect of oxalic acid concentration on the reaction between methylene blue and titanium(III) in the range of 0.005 M- 0.05 M and found that the effect of change in oxalic acid concentration is negligible. We have found the similar observation in the case of cacotheline and thionine as indicators. Thus the high values obtained for quinone¹ can be improved in the presence of oxalic acid.

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Synthesis and Iodination of 5,6-benzo-4'-hydroxyflavanone

S.V. KUBERKAR and U.K. JAGWANI

Department of Chemistry, Yeshwant Mahavidyalaya,
Nanded, Maharashtra

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IN continuation of our previous work,^{1,2} carried out in this laboratory, iodination of 5,6-benzo-4'-hydroxyflavanone has been studied.

1-Acetyl-2-naphthol and *p*-hydroxy benzaldehyde when condensed in the presence of potassium hydroxide gave a product which did not give any colour with alcoholic ferric chloride solution and a Wilson test³. 5,6-Benzo-4'-hydroxyflavanone structure, therefore, assigned to the above product. This was further confirmed on the basis of analysis of its acetyl derivative.

5,6-Benzo-4' hydroxyflavanone on iodination with theoretical amounts of iodine and iodic acid gave a mono-iododerivative which was converted into diiododerivative by further iodination with iodine and iodic acid. The same diiodo derivative could also be obtained from 5,6-benzo-4'-hydroxyflavanone with twice the amount of iodine and iodic acid. The diiododerivative on methylation gave the same product as obtained by the condensation of 3,5-diiodoanisaldehyde⁴ with 1-acetyl-2-naphthol in the presence of potassium hydroxide. Therefore, 3'-iodo- and 3'-5'-diiodo-4' hydroxy-5,6 benzoflavanone structures were assigned to the mono and diiodo derivative respectively. Triiodo derivative could not be obtained even with excess of iodinating agents.

In case of sodium salt of monoiodo derivative, when tested for the toxicity to fish⁵⁻⁹, the turning point of the fish¹⁰ was observed in 8 minutes while in case of sodium salt of diiododerivative the turning point was observed in 5 min.

Experimental

5,6-Benzo-4'-hydroxyflavanone (I), 3'-iodo (II), 3'-5'-diiodo-4'-hydroxy (III), 4'-methoxyflavanone (IV), were prepared according to the procedure described in the paper^{1,2}. 5,6-Benzo-4'-acetoxyflavanone (V) was prepared by heating the above flavanone (1g) acetic anhydride (5 ml.) fused sodium acetate (1.5g) for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was poured in ice cold water, and the product crystallised from glacial acetic acid.

The purity of all the compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography on silicagel, using benzene and ethyl acetate (85 : 15) as the developer solvents.